

Local extrema at a prism with two functions

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We view the prism (the cylinder) in the figure:

We want to determine the extremum volume of the prism (cylinder). To the base of a prism we obtain as before:

$$G = nx^2 \cdot \cos \alpha \sin \alpha \quad \alpha = \frac{\pi}{n}$$

with the addition theorem:

$$G = \frac{n}{2} \cdot \sin \left(\frac{2\pi}{n} \right) \cdot x^2$$

At the circular cylinder:

$$G = \pi \cdot x^2$$

We obtain $h = y_1 - y_2$ as height with $y_1 = f_1(x)$ and $y_2 = f_2(x)$. We get to the cylinder's volume:

$$V = \pi x^2 \cdot (y_1 - y_2)$$

Derivative:

$$V' = \pi \cdot (x^2 \cdot (y_1' - y_2') + 2x \cdot (y_1 - y_2))$$

The necessary criterion $V' = 0$ of local extrema leads to:

$$x \cdot (y_1' - y_2') + 2 \cdot (y_1 - y_2) = 0$$

For the prism we can do the calculation in the same way. The derivation distinguishes only through a factor. Instead of π we have $\frac{n}{2} \cdot \sin \left(\frac{2\pi}{n} \right)$. The criterion of

local extrema remains unchanged.

Special cases: $c = \text{const.}$

$$y_1 = c \quad \text{it follows} \quad 2 \cdot (c - y_2) - xy'_2 = 0$$

$$y_2 = c \quad \text{it follows} \quad 2 \cdot (y_1 - c) + xy'_1 = 0$$

Extremum lateral area:

The prism's perimeter is:

$$U = 2n \cdot x \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right)$$

for the circular cylinder:

$$U = \pi \cdot x$$

We obtain to the lateral area:

$$M = U \cdot h \quad \text{with} \quad h = y_1 - y_2$$

for the circular cylinder:

$$M = \pi \cdot x \cdot (y_1 - y_2)$$

derived:

$$M' = \pi \cdot (y_1 - y_2 + x \cdot (y'_1 - y'_2))$$

The necessary criterion $M' = 0$ of local extrema leads to:

$$y_1 - y_2 + x \cdot (y'_1 - y'_2) = 0$$

For the prism we can do the the same calculation. Instead of π we need the factor $2n \cdot \sin \frac{\pi}{n}$. The criterion of local extrema remains unchanged.

Special cases: $c = \text{const.}$

$$y_1 = c \quad \Rightarrow \quad c - y_2 - xy'_2 = 0$$

$$y_2 = c \quad \Rightarrow \quad y_1 - c + xy'_1 = 0$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder, "Special extreme value problems and extremum principles",
Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002